

IOT-BASED POND MANAGEMENT FOR FRESHWATER FISH

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Abstract. The proponents assume that several elements or criteria can be the cause of fish mortality in the pond, but some of them have little or no influence on it. As a result, the advocates selected the parameters of water temperature, pH level, turbidity, and water level. The proponents find that certain information they acquired on the internet for establishing the threshold level of each criterion for the fish kill differs from what the proponents were taught by the fish farmers. The proponents conclude that the project IoT-Based Pond Management for Freshwater Fish will assist fish pond owners and farmers in adding a system that will assist them in monitoring the various fishes in their pond to avoid the scenario of fish kill, which is common during the dry season or summer. It obtained a high percentage of efficacy and usefulness from a survey completed by fishpond owners and farmers. To prevent unpleasant scenarios, the proponent suggests fish pond owners use all current and elevated IT hardware or sensors while implementing the IoT-Based Pond Management for Freshwater Fish in their pond. Each fish farmer and owner should have access to a mobile application that allows them to manually run the system.

Keywords. Pond Management, Internet of Things, Freshwater Fish, Aquaculture

1 Introduction

A fishpond is an artificial lake or a place where fish is being stored that has been used to produce fish that are being sold in public markets or by fish vendors. This type is usually used for aquaculture, which means that it is for growing fish in a particular pond, and the pond is readily made so they do not escape, allowing fish to be fed, bred, grown, and of course for harvesting the fish to be sold. However, the mortality of the fish in a pond is a natural process and can be noticed occasionally.

One of the things that have an impact on fish kill is climate change which includes almost all aspects of fish kill such as the shift in temperature where fish may die due to temperature that may change uncontrollably, acidification where it is the acidity of the water due to increase of carbon dioxide concentration and lowering of pH level. Another factor of fish kill is clay or mud, silt, or tiny inorganic and organic matter and chemical nature. Dissolved oxygen is also one of the causes of fish kill due to the warm water of the pond mostly holding less dissolved oxygen because the warm water is more significant than cold water (Aqua Sierra Biologist, November 21, 2016). And the last factor the fish kills is ammonia, which is because of the protein in the feed. In General Santos City, another fish kill occurred and drastically hit Lake Sebu in South Cotabato on January 8, 2021. This led to a massive emergency harvesting of the fish to save the remaining tilapia in the pond. This incident occurred because of what they called "kamahong" - a phenomenon mainly caused by a sudden rise of water's temperature due to a lack of monitoring system for the ponds (Philippine News Agency, Allen Estabillo). Other news reported the massive death of fish stocks in certain areas due to unfavorable water quality (De Vera-Ruiz, E., 2021).

This prototype already exists, and many have done it, but much more can be done, and much more can be improved. This prototype cannot be configured, but the proponents assume that it can be set to a set temperature, etc., even while putting different types of fish in their pond.

For this proposal, the proponents decided to develop and innovate the existing project by adding some features and functions for the fish kill monitoring system. The proponents chose to measure the temperature in water on the pond, pH level, turbidity, ammonia, and dissolved oxygen. They are using the open-source electronic platform as the microcontroller and act as the system's brain. The waterproof temperature sensor is used to monitor the water temperature in the fishpond; when the sensor detects abnormalities in temperature, the water pump is triggered to maintain the average temperature of the water in the pond. Using a temperature sensor, the owner can control the temperature of the fish pond. If the temperature of the fishpond increases, the waterfalls for circulation activate because

circulation is the secret to keeping the water cold. Using the water level sensor, the owner can know if the water in the pond is going down and up and keep it at its proper size.

The proponents are motivated to develop this project to help our fish farming monitor the daily nature or condition of the water in the fishpond due to different and uncontrollable reasons and factors that lead to fish kills. And also to contribute to advanced fish farming using technology and extending knowledge to enrich, solve, and help fish farming to have a good production of fish.

2 Review of Related Literature

Commercial fish farming has also proved to be a profitable venture, A lucrative business enterprise worldwide. Fish is a high-protein and high-calorie food. Fish is a nutrient-dense food that is also one of the world's healthiest foods. It's loaded with nutrients like protein, vitamins, and minerals. Choosing the suitable fish species for your fish farming company is critical if you want to make the most money. Choose breeds in high demand and sell for a high price in your region. Carp, tilapia, and milkfish are the most common fish species used in fish farming worldwide. (Roy's Farm, 2021) In the developed world like the Philippines, fish is significant. Most people eat fish because fish is the healthiest food in the world. You can be sure that the fish in the ponds is super clean to eat because it is cared for and raised healthy for sale in the market. Fish is good for your body because of the nutrients, protein, vitamins, and minerals they give to your body.

Fish pond development is critical for lake residents' income, survival, and domestic fish availability. However, the occurrence and recurrence of fish killings result in substantial economic losses every year. When adaptive solutions are found, the advocates investigate the causes of fish kills and their replication. The findings indicate that fish kills are caused by environmental and human pressures and the mismanagement of the lake's resources. Because of the relationship between water temperature, dissolved oxygen, and decomposition by-products, overfeeding and overuse of the lake are essential facts in fish-killing (i.e., ammonia nitrogen and H₂S). It's helpful to keep track of critical water temperature and dissolved oxygen levels when predicting fish kills. Finally, since the lake is an expected resource with multiple uses, the fishing cage industry needs a multi-sector management approach (Nieves et al., 2020). The most popular reason for fish death is a lack of dissolved oxygen in the water. To live, fish, like all other complex life forms, need oxygen. They get it in the form of liquefied oxygen gas in water.

Consequently, any factor that causes a decrease in oxygen in the water may kill fish. Overpopulation, water toxicity, and algae bloom are examples of such causes. Algae carry out photosynthesis with the aid of oxygen. That's why using this system can reduce the effects and cause of fish kills in fish ponds resulting in good production of fish.

A fish kill occurs when many cultured or wild fish and other marine animals such as prawns die suddenly and unexpectedly. Since the water is warmer during the summer, it happens more often. Warm water has a lower concentration of dissolved oxygen than cold water. As a result, the fish have more trouble breathing, eventually dying in warm water. Fish kills are a sign of stress in the ecosystem. To avoid further fish deaths, they should be examined as soon as they are reported. Both natural and artificial causes cause fish kills. As a result, algae in the water reduce the oxygen available to the fish. Aside from algae, an overabundance of aquatic life deprives fish of much-needed oxygen. Another factor that contributes to fish deaths is toxicity. It's a term for water contamination caused by farm runoff. Hazardous waste spills, chemical poaching, sewage discharge, and underwater explosions can cause toxicity.

When it comes to water temperature, fish kills are average during prolonged periods of high temperatures. Because of the high temperatures, less oxygen is dissolved in the water. (Omondi, 2018). With the use of this system, the fish kill can be reduced by monitoring the temperature, pH level, water level turbidity, and ammonia. The recent fish kill off Las Piñas and Parañaque in Manila Bay, where at least 30 tubs of dead fish were discovered along the coastline, was caused by water contamination rather than blast fishing. According to him, water quality studies revealed low dissolved oxygen levels and high levels of ammonia and phosphates caused by animal waste and sewage. Agricultural, residential, and industrial wastes may have contributed to the ammonia in the water supply. (Cruz, 2019).

According to Canlas, five tons of tilapia worth P4.5 million have been discovered dead and floating in Lake Sebu in South Cotabato. According to local officials, the fish kill impacted over 300 fish cage operators. When the assessment is completed, the number is expected to increase. The fish kill affected at least 90% of the fish cages. Tilapia fingerlings

worth P225,000 were lost by one of the affected operators. He claims the fish kill was caused by nonstop rains last week. According to the town's agriculturist, the fish kill was caused by a shortage of oxygen. (Canlas, 2017) Many fish dying suddenly, or fish gasping at the surface, suggests an oxygen shortage caused by inadequate aeration, elevated temperatures, or overcrowding of fish or plants.

A fish kill that affected 130 hectares of fishpond areas in Obando, Bulacan, cost at least P29 million in Bangus (milkfish). Due to oxygen depletion, 250 metric tons of bangus in 40 operators' fish pens in seven barangays of the town died. The fish kill occurred at midnight, triggered by unfavorable environmental factors, the especially intense heat of 34 °C, which coincided with a low tide level of 0.050 meters. The causes of dissolved oxygen depletion, which led to the fish kill, were light rain showers, endless cloudy skies, and thermal variations in the water due to changing weather conditions. (Cordero, 2018).

It's essential to identify the cause and effects of fish kills to differentiate between natural and human-caused incidents so that this system can decide whether or not remedial steps are required to resolve the cause and avoid further fish kills because this system can help determine the causes of future fish kills.

The most significant impediments to modernizing fish ponds in this area are capital and operational costs in an otherwise lucrative sector, namely food processing. Small-scale farmers with small ponds couldn't afford to employ staff to manage their daily activities, which usually include controlling water levels, temperature, and fish feeding. Water monitoring and replacement automation are commonly used in larger-scale businesses. As their farms expand, these organizations may need to consider using pH and dissolved oxygen (DO) sensors to ensure the health and growth of their fish. As long as users have access to the internet, they obtain information at predetermined intervals on their chosen communication or display devices. This farm has high-quality water, according to two days of temperature, pH, and DO measurements. The pond's oxygen levels rise throughout the day as photosynthesis is assisted by the sun. The pond's oxygen levels rise throughout the day as photosynthesis is administered by the sun. This integration system eliminates the need for farmers to employ workers on-site, lowering operating costs and increasing production. (Harun et al., 2018)

The temperature affects fish growth and survival. Variations in size, such as weight and length, may be a choice for how temperature affects fish development. Since people like heavy and oversized fish, this may be a crucial factor in deciding supply as well as consumer demand. The fundamental goal of this research was to see how temperature affected milkfish development in terms of weight and length in fish farms. For growth and survival, fish need a specific temperature. Depending on the age and size of the fish, the ideal temperature is adjusted. Fish enjoy colder conditions when they are younger than when they are adults.

Like all living creatures, fish have a particular tolerant set of different environmental parameters, so fish farming of unique types of fish species necessitates the achievement of specific requirements. The pond "does" have no particular temperature. Of course, you would need a warm aquarium if you keep tropical fish. But it's an expensive effort to keep a pond wet while the wind works against you. It's also worthless to hold cold-water fish such as tropical trout. You better choose fish that are appropriate for your setting. The emphasis should be on preventing rapid temperature variations. The pH of water indicates whether it is acidic or basic. Since fish have an average blood pH of 7.4, pond water with a pH of 7.4 is ideal. A range of 6.5 to 9.0 would be appropriate. In water with a pH of 4.0 to 6.5 and 9.0 to 11.0, fish may become stressed. The amount of ammonia in the air should be kept as low as possible. Ideally, they should be at 0 ppm, but if your pH level is neutral, they can be at 0.5 ppm. Bear in mind that the higher your pH, the more poisonous ammonia becomes, so it's best to keep it down. Similarly, Nitrites should be held as low as possible, preferably below 0.25ppm.

Agriculture serves as an essential act globally by meeting one of a person's basic needs, namely food, even though assets are depleting daily. A slew of other issues arise, regardless of prejudices. When other technology fails to detect a crop's routine, automation occurs by linking to invincible storage such as the cloud and streamlining the operation by finding the hardware and introducing a user-friendly internet platform. The Internet of Things (IoT) has set a new standard in technology and has become a foundation for agriculture. This technological innovation aids in farming automation, which aids in shaping a farmer's workspace, ensuring system management, communication management, efficiency as a result, and remote control. This paper discusses IoT basics, agriculture IoT, emerging wireless IoT technologies, IoT architectures, and IoT applications. (Lova Raju & Vijayaraghavan, 2020)

The Internet of Things (IoT) is one of the fastest-growing fields for providing social and financial points of interest for growing and expanding a nation's economy. The Internet of Things (IoT) is currently thriving in medicine, agriculture, transportation, and training. Since aquaculture is a backward branch of applied science, this is important. Compared to other areas such as agriculture, it is critical to use technology to identify the issues in this region. Aquaculture is raising aquatic organisms in natural or artificial marine or freshwater habitats. Both shrimp aquaculture and paddy farming depend heavily on real-time monitoring of environmental parameters. This paper proposes an electronic framework to efficiently monitor and control various environmental parameters related to paddy fields and shrimp aquaculture. (Kumar et al., 2020).

3 Project Design and Methodology

The proposed project, IoT-Based Pond Management for Freshwater Fish, contributes and helps the freshwater fishpond farmers to monitor their fishponds in terms of water turbidity, temperature, level, ammonia, and pH level of the water in fishpond that help to lessen the phenomena where fish die because of this parameter which were uncontrollably changing without knowing. The proponents of the study used an Operational Framework that served as the basis of the project (shown in Figure 1).

Upon building and creating this project, the project used an open-source electronic platform, and all sensors and modules were connected here. They are using the open-source electronic platform as the microcontroller and act as the brain of the system. All data gathered from the sensors and modules is sent to a mobile application through an internet connection. If there's no internet connection, a Bluetooth connection can send all data and information to the mobile application. The LCDs are the information sent to the mobile application, such as temperature, ammonia level, turbidity level, water level, dissolved oxygen, and pH level.

A water temperature sensor is used to monitor the water temperature in the fishpond; when the sensor detects abnormalities in temperature, the water pump is triggered to maintain the average temperature of the water on the pond. Using a temperature sensor, the owner can control the temperature of the fish pond. If the temperature of the fishpond increases, the waterfalls for circulation activate because circulation is the secret to keeping the water cold. The proponents use two (2) water pumps for water circulation to maintain the average water temperature in the pond. If the temperature is too high, the two (2) water pumps trigger circulation to lower the water temperature in the pond.

Figure 1. Operational Framework for the Proposed Project

The water level sensor lets the owner know if the water in the pond is going up or down and keeps the water at its proper size. This helps understand if the water level is increasing/decreasing because of hot weather and rainfall. The proponents use two (2) water pumps to maintain the pond's water level. Suppose the water level sensor detects that the water is increasing. In that case, the water pump trigger where the water in the fish pond be reduced and go to the water container. In contrast, if the water level sensor detects that the water is decreasing, the water pump triggers the fish pond filled with water from the water container.

For pH level, the proponents use a pH meter sensor to measure the acidity and basicity of the water. Reading it, it ranges from 1 to 14 readings with 1 being for the most acidic and 14 for the most basic. Using the pH water level sensor, the owner can monitor and control the pH level of the ponds. The pond owner can add organic matter to the fish pond if the pH level increases. This organic matter is carbon dioxide, acting as an acid in water. Adding organic matter into a fish pond is a safer and long-lasting way to reduce high pH in water, but too much carbon dioxide can dissolve oxygen.

A dissolved oxygen sensor kit for monitoring the dissolved oxygen in the fishpond helps the fish have good breathing functionality to survive. A turbidity sensor monitors the water quality because it may change due to particles that mix with the water like it stirs up the bottom mud. This can also be fixed by adding Epsom salts and aluminum sulfate, which clear the muddy ponds and do not affect the water's pH level.

And last, ammonia sensors are used for monitoring the ammonia level in the fishpond. Too many proteins in food for fish and other toxic materials in the water may increase the ammonia level, resulting in fish kills. This can be treated by adding chopped hay by using a servo motor to reduce the ammonia in the pond.

The mobile application is used to configure and monitor the changes within the fish pond. The users can configure the system according to what the system needs, such as the range of water temperature of the fish pond, the water level of the fish pond, turbidity in the fish pond, dissolved oxygen in the fish pond, ammonia level in the pond and pH level of the water in the fish pond. The Bluetooth connection serves as the backup connection if there is no Wi-Fi connection. The changes in the system notify the owners through the web application.

4 Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows the layout of IoT-Based Pond Management for Freshwater Fish; this wireframe contains wirings and sensors that are connected using the open-source electronic platform as the microcontroller and acting as the brain of the system, which is the Arduino Uno. This module and sensors are a water temperature sensor, float switch sensor, pH meter sensor, and turbidity sensor.

Figure 2. Wireframe Design of IoT-Based Pond Management for Freshwater Fish

The modules, sensors, and the system's brain, the Nodemcu, make up the hardware portion of the project. The ESP32 is a family of low-cost, low-power system-on-a-chip microcontrollers with built-in Wi-Fi and dual-mode Bluetooth. This would store the codes and programs for the sensors and modules, allowing them to work as needed. To complete the installation of all modules and sensors, Figure 18 shows the pH level sensor, which has 3 pins, GND, VCC, and SDA. The GND pin is connected to negative, VCC is connected to 5v or positive, while the SDA is connected to D35. The pH level sensor can detect if the water is already acidic. And when the pH level sensor continuously monitors the value of the pH level. At pH level, the normal range or the needed of the fish is 6-8. The proponents set the pH level. If the pH level detects that the water is already acidic, the mobile application sends an email message to the owner and fish farmer.

Figure 3. Installing pH Level

For the water temperature, the proponents used the water temperature sensor, which senses or detects the temperature of the water continuously. The water temperature sensor ground is connected to the ground pin, the vcc pin is connected to 5v and the sig pin is connected to D19. In the temperature sensor, the normal temperature that fish needed was between 24 and 32 degrees Celsius because each fish needs a different water temperature for bangus 26 to 30 degrees celcius.

To check the mud of the water, the proponents used a Turbidity sensor to measure the quality of water whether it is clear cloudy, or dirty. Figure 20 shows the turbidity sensor with 4 pins, but the proponents used only 3 pins. G, A, and V, G are for the ground, A is for the SM or D39, and V is for 5v. The proponents set the turbidity range into 1-5, 1-2 for muddy, 3 for cloudy, and 4-5 for clean water.

Figure 4. Installing turbidity sensor

For the water level, the proponents used two water level float sensors to monitor, they have 2 pins, ground, and pins. The float switch is for the minimum of water, and the second one is for the maximum water. The pin of the first float is D26, and the second one is D27. In water float sensor detects the water level. If the sensor detects that the water is increasing, the water pump is triggered and decreases the water.

The proponents used two pieces of a 16x2 LCD with 20 pins total for displaying the value of pH level, turbidity, and water temperature, as shown in Figure 5. Still, the proponents encountered a problem with the number of pins that contradicted the number of pins on the Nodemcu baseboard, so the proponents used an I2C module that converts I2C serial data to parallel data LCD. The I2C module was used to transform the 16 pins into 4 pins, with the earth pin linked to the ground, the vcc pin connected to the 5v power supply, the sda pin, and the SCL pin.

Figure 5. Installing LCD

Figure 6. Actual Picture of the Mobile Application

In Figure 6, the proponents finish the final output of the mobile application. In the first screen, the proponents put a pH level, temperature, turbidity, water level, and intelligent feeding icon so that the respondents can easily recognize what that icon is. In the smart feeding icon and configuration text, there are buttons so the respondents can click the icon and text, and the respondents go to the configuration screen.

Testing a prototype is an essential part of the design and manufacturing process to ensure user satisfaction. The proponents made a system test, and the hardware test functioning through automated testing to ensure that the code satisfied its design and requirements as expected.

Figure 7. The Actual Model of Fish Pond Prototype

In this phase, testing also aids in the detection of any flaws, allowing the designer to adjust. The user can inspect the prototype and provide feedback during testing and evaluation. Changes and enhancements are agreed upon, and additional work is completed. A focus group can test the prototype and provide feedback on it. At this stage, flaws and difficulties are frequently discovered. At this point, it's helpful to make suggestions for improvement, and it is possible to use the results from this phase to reduce the errors within the proposed project.

Figure 7 shows the actual model of the fish pond in which the modules are installed in the proper places. The proponents present the project to the fish pond owner to see if it is beneficial and feasible. If the water is cloudy, the system automatically activates the turbidity sensor; if the water contains too much acid, the system automatically activates the Ph level sensor; if the water level rises or falls, the flow switch automatically activates; if the water temperature is too hot, the water temperature sensor automatically activates; and when the feeding time has been reached, the servo motor automatically turns on. The data that each sensor had been detected automatically sent and displayed on the LCD.

During this phase, the proponents went to Brgy. Quinton, San Carlos City, Pangasinan, to present the fish pond prototype from the owners and explain and discuss all the features of the prototype. After presenting the project to the respondents, they were given an evaluation form to answer and evaluate the project.

Figure 7. Proponents Presenting the Prototype

The respondents are satisfied with what they see and ask if the proponents can deploy it in the real fish pond. The respondents gave their suggestions and thoughts about the project/prototype. After the demonstration of the prototype to the respondents, the proponents survey the respondents on the prototype they discuss.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

The proponents conclude that many factors or criteria can be a cause of fish kill in the pond, but some of it doesn't have any big impact on it. So, the proponents chose the parameters of water temperature, pH level, turbidity, and water level. The proponents conclude that some information they found on the internet for determining the threshold level of each criterion for the fish kill is different from what the fish farmers said to the proponents.

The proponents conclude that every fish has a different water temperature; for tilapia, it must be 26°C to 32°C, and for the milkfish, it must be 22°C to 28°C. The pH level of the water is 6 to 8 ranging in the normal pH level of water that the fish need and the turbidity of the water must not be too muddy. The proponents still need to calibrate the sensors to be able to determine the normal and above or below normal to prevent fish kill scenarios in the pond.

The proponents conclude that the project IoT-Based Pond Management for Freshwater Fish help the fish pond owners and farmers add a system that helps them monitor the different fishes in their pond to prevent the scenario of fish kill primarily during this time of dry season or summer, where it received a high percentage of effectivity and usability from the survey answered by the fishpond owners and farmers.

The proponent advises fish pond owners to employ all current and high-quality IT equipment or sensors while installing the IoT-Based Pond Management for Freshwater Fish in their pond to avoid adverse scenarios. Each fish farmer and the owner should have access to a mobile application that allows them to operate the system manually. Fish farmers and owners should prepare extra batteries and internet connections for emergencies.

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